

Small Bowel Obstruction Due to Strangulated Transomental Internal Hernia: A Case Report

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Abstract

Small bowel obstruction secondary to internal hernias is rare, accounting for less than 1% of all cases. We report the case of a 74-year-old male patient with a history of diabetes, occasional alcohol consumption, and chronic smoking. He presented with symptoms of sub-occlusive syndrome including cessation of stool passage without cessation of flatus, diffuse abdominal distension, and bilious vomiting. Abdominal computed tomography (CT) revealed small bowel dilation with air-fluid levels and a transition point in the right flank. Exploratory laparotomy identified a 2.5 cm defect in the greater omentum containing a viable incarcerated small bowel loop. Surgical reduction of the herniated loop and resection of the omental defect were performed. Postoperative recovery was uneventful.

Keywords: *Small bowel obstruction, internal hernia, transomental hernia.*

Introduction

Internal hernias are rare but important causes of small bowel obstruction (Hasnaoui, et al., 2019), accounting for approximately 0.5–1% of cases annually (Echaïeb, et al., 2023). Among them, omental hernias represent 1–4% and are often diagnosed intraoperatively (Echaïeb, et al., 2023). We present a case of sub-occlusive syndrome secondary to a transomental hernia, along with a brief literature review.

Case Presentation

A 74-year-old man with type 2 diabetes treated with oral antidiabetics, occasional alcohol use, and chronic smoking presented with signs of sub-occlusive syndrome. Symptoms included cessation of stool passage with continued passage of flatus, diffuse abdominal distension, and bilious vomiting, without deterioration of general condition.

On examination, the patient was conscious and hemodynamically stable. Abdominal examination revealed a distended and tympanic abdomen, and digital rectal exam showed an empty rectal ampulla.

Abdominal CT (figure 1) revealed small bowel dilation with a maximum diameter of 53 mm and air-fluid levels, along with a transition point in the right flank and fat stranding in the surrounding mesentery.

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Figure 1. CT Scan Showing Small Bowel Distension and Transition Point

Surgical exploration via midline laparotomy revealed a 2.5 cm defect in the greater omentum containing (figure 2) a closed but viable small bowel loop located approximately 3.8 meters distal to the duodenojejunal junction and 60 cm proximal to the ileocecal junction. Surgical management consisted of hernia reduction and resection of the omental defect.

Figure 2. Intraoperative View of the Incarcerated Bowel Loop

Postoperative recovery was uneventful, with return of bowel function within 24 hours. The patient was discharged 48 hours postoperatively and was seen in follow-up 6 weeks later with complete recovery and normal daily activity.

Discussion

Acute small bowel obstruction is a surgical emergency, most often due to adhesions (Ishigami, et al., 2000), external hernias, or tumors. Internal hernias, though rare, should be considered, especially in the absence of prior abdominal surgery or external hernias (Camera, et al., 2014). In our case, the presumed cause was degenerative changes in the greater omentum leading to a defect through which the bowel herniated (Chaouch, et al., 2024).

Clinical presentation is often nonspecific, including abdominal pain, vomiting, and distension. Physical examination may reveal a tympanic abdomen and an empty rectal ampulla, suggestive of intestinal obstruction (Buan, Lwin, & Cheong, 2022; Endou, et al. 2002).

CT is essential for diagnosis, typically showing dilated bowel loops, air-fluid levels, and a transition point suggestive of obstruction (Camera, et al, 2014), along with signs of bowel compromise when present (Camera, et al, 2014; Ishigami, et al., 2000).

Prompt surgical exploration is critical to confirm diagnosis, assess bowel viability, and prevent complications (Chaouch, et al., 2024; Ahn, et al., 2022). While laparotomy was performed in this case, laparoscopy can be a valuable alternative offering advantages such as minimally invasive access and better visualization of the abdominal cavity. However, ischemic bowel may limit its use (Yagyu, et al., 2024).

Conclusion

Transomental internal hernias are a rare but important cause of small bowel obstruction. Surgeons should maintain a high index of suspicion, especially in the absence of prior surgery. Abdominal CT plays a key role in diagnosis. Timely surgical intervention—whether via laparoscopy or laparotomy—is crucial for confirming the diagnosis, relieving the obstruction, and preventing complications.

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